

THE ROLE OF IMITATIVE WORDS IN THE STRUCTURE OF A SENTENCE IN THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7482157>

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***Abstract:** In the Uzbek language, imitative expressions are categorized as a separate word group between independent and non-independent word groups at the morphological level, and in English linguistics, imitative words and independent words formed from imitation are called onomatopes, but at the morphological level, independent words made from imitation belong to one of the existing independent word groups according to their grammatical signs identified. The purpose of the article is to identify the typological features of modern English and Uzbek imitative words, semantic and contextual description, showing the norm of constant use, translation problems.*

Key word: *imitative words, onomatopoeia, linguistic aspect, morphological structure, lexical meaning, stylistic purposes*

Words that imitate the sound and state of things are imitative words. Imitative words are of two types according to what they mean:

1. Imitation of sound. It means imitating the sound of things. It is also called onomatopoeic words. Example: *ap-ap, вақ-вақ, вии, вов, гум-гум, дўн-дўн, нуқ-нуқ, му-му.*

2. Imitation of the situation. It means imitation of the state of things. Example: *биж-биж, вижир-вижир, даг-даг, мўлт-мўлт, ялт-юлт*.

Repetitive word parts are separated by hyphens.

Words that arise by imitation of various sounds in the objective world and figurative states of the movement of things and events are called imitative words.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, imitative words are understood as words that imitate different sounds and images [1]. Sound imitation is associated with hearing, figurative imitation is associated with vision, that is, the sound imitated by sound can only be heard. Example: *қарс-қурс, тақ, дук-дук, қийқ, миёв*; the situation represented by words imitating the image, the action can only be seen. Example: *живир-живир, лип-лип, ялт-юлт, ҳанг-манг* and others.

In dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics the term ‘Onomatopoeia’ (noun) – also sound symbolism, echoism. Refers to words that are considered by convention to be imitative of nature, acoustically similar to the thing to which it refers (*e.g. the bow-wow of a dog or the tick-tock of a clock*) or the sound made by the thing to which it refers (*a buzz saw*). There are other words that are examples of semi-onomatopoeia, such as the English words *splash or growl*. Languages differ in the range, choice, and phonetic realizations of onomatopoeic words. An English *dog goes bow-bow or ruff-ruff; or woof-woof*; a Japanese one goes *wan-wan* [5].

In dictionary of Linguistic Terms ‘Onomatopoeia’ (ОНОМАТОПЕЯ) – onomatopoeia means sound symbolism (echoism), in French language ‘onomatopée’, in Spanish language ‘onomatopeya’. 1. Conditional reproduction of the sounds of nature and the sounds that accompany certain processes (*trembling, laughter, whistling, etc.*), as well as the cries of animals. For example: *meow, woof-woof, crow*. 2. The creation of words, the sound shells of which, to one degree or another, resemble the named (denoted) objects and phenomena. For example: *laughter, cuckoo, purr* [2]. Theory of onomatopoeia (onomatopoeic theory) in English ‘onomatopoeic theory’. One of the hypotheses about the origin

of the language, according to which the language arose due to the fact that a person imitated natural sounds, gradually giving them a schematic and conditional form [2].

Conjugation of imitative words

Imitative words sometimes become nouns and receive plural, possessive, and agreement suffixes. For example: *Қулогимга хумга тушган арининг овозидай кўнғир-кўнғир гаплашганлари эшитилар эди* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 47) – *And they talked to each-other* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 39). In this sentence, we drop the noun group and transfer the possessive suffix of the noun to the imitative word. For example: *Қулогимга хумга тушган арининг овозидай кўнғир-кўнғирлари эшитилар эди* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 47).

–**group of nouns.** Example: *“Бай-бай”, гапнинг айни қизгин жойида қочган экансан* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 98) – *Oh, you ran away at the interesting part* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 84);

–**group of adjective.** Example: *Унинг настак-настак пахса деворлари кўриниб қолди* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 72) – *Its short mud bricks were seen* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 63);

–**group of phrasal verb.** Example: *Ярим кечада ой кўтарилгандан кейин, олдинма-кетин хуштак чалишиб, “қур-ей, қур-ей, қур-ей”lashib, Кўктеракка қараб кета бошладик* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 71) – *At midnight, when the moon rose to the sky, we started our journey to Kekterak whistling and saying “query qurey”* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 62);

–**other verb forms.** Example: *Омонни талади, қишлоқнинг ҳар томонидан вовиллашиб бошқа итлар етиб келди* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 89) – *Then, we faced a dog. It tried to bite Omon* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 75).

Imitative words are the basis for the formation of verbs: *шовулламоқ, гумбурламоқ,*

дупирламоқ, қарсилламоқ, ялтирамоқ.

Sometimes imitative words can be the basis for the formation of nouns, adjectives

and adverbs.

Noun: *хуррак, шақилдоқ*

Adjective: *чийилдоқ, шаррос, шартаки*

Adverb: *чиппа, гуппа, шартта, таққа*

Example: Омон менга жавоб бермасдан ўзининг “қур-ей”и билан овора бўлди (Ғафур Ғулом. Шум бола, 73) – Omon didn’t answer and was busy with saying “querey, querey” (Gafur Gulom. A Naughty Boy, 63)

Хотин дағ-дағ қалтирар эди (Ғафур Ғулом. Шум бола, 48) – The woman was shivering (Gafur Gulom. A Naughty Boy, 40).

Ўша ерда мен жуда ҳам беҳуд бўлиб, “қийқ” этиб ўзимдан кеттим (Ғафур Ғулом. Шум бола, 50) – I was really exhausted so I fainted (Gafur Gulom. A Naughty Boy, 42)

*Уч-тўрт жойига **гарам-гарам** ҳўл бедалар уйиб ташиланган (Ғафур Ғулом. Шум бола, 105) – There were clovers on the tree (Gafur Gulom. A Naughty Boy, 90).*

Imitative words formed by the exact repetition of the main part or repetition with some sound changes are considered repeated imitative words: *гумбур-гумбур, қурс-қурс, чарс-чурс, тақ-туқ, ярқ-юрқ*

R.Kongurov emphasizes that although figurative words and sound imitation words are close to each other as a grammatical category from the phonetic, morphological and syntactic aspects, they have their own characteristics [6]:

1. From the semantic point of view, sound imitation words appear as a result of imitating the sounds made by people, birds and animals, as well as inanimate objects. They are mainly connected with hearing. Figurative words come to the field as a result of vision and express the imaginary images of the state, movement and appearance of people and other animate and inanimate objects. For example: a) idiomatic words: *мўлт-мўлт, зивир-зивир, апил-тапил, бижир-бижир* [1]; b)

words that imitate the sound: *вақ-вақ, гангир-гунгур, данг-дунг, зув-зув, пинг-понгб, зат-зат* [1].

Onomatopoeic words indicate more speed and immediacy, while figurative words show instantity and immediacy, and can also reflect a full complex of imagination.

2. Figurative words are genetically more closely related to independent words. There is no connection between sound complexes in figurative words and the phenomena they describe. In words that imitate sound, sound complexes appear as conditional copies of sounds in nature. They are directly related to the events they represent.

That is, the proximity between the meaning of figurative words such as *лапанг-лапанг, талтанг-талтанг, лип-лип, гилт-гилт* and the sound complex is conditional, *шарт-шурт, зирч-зирч, гилт-гилт* is fundamentally different from the closeness between the words and their meaning.

3. Words imitating the sound can be combined with auxiliary verbs such as *этмоқ, демоқ* and figurative words are combined with the auxiliary verb *этмоқ*.

Imitative words are used a lot in fiction, oral speech, and folklore, they give speech artistic color and expressiveness. At the same time, they are of great importance as a reflection of objective existence and as a building material in language.

It is obvious that the writers used imitative words for stylistic purposes. There are even cases where the meaning of the sentence is not fully understood if the similes are removed. With the appropriate use of the word imitation, expressiveness and artistry are added to the sentence, at the same time, the meaning is made concrete and clarified. Example: *Ўйнаб-кулиб, таралангни тортиб юравер. Сенга “чурқ” этадиганнинг боши ўнта* (Ғафур Ғулом. *Шум бола*, 128) – *If anybody frightens you, his head will be ten* (Gafur Gulom. *A Naughty Boy*, 108).